

proof of Pythagorean theorem through cosine law

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Proof

cosine law for angle γ :

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab\cos\gamma$$

according to the problem statement: $\gamma = 90^\circ \Rightarrow c^2 = a^2 + b^2$

Pythagoras' theorem is proven